

GENERAL LECTURE 6

ACM Reinforcement Fiber Production and Its Application in Japan

M. Tatsuhana

Torayca Business, Toray Industries, Inc., 2-2 Nihonbashi-Muromachi, Chuo-ku, Tokyo 103, Japan

ABSTRACT

This paper presents the ACM reinforcement fiber production and its application status in Japan. The emphasis is specially placed on PAN carbon fiber production and its application development. The developments of pitch based Carbon Fiber, Aramid Fiber and Silicone Carbide Fiber in Japan are also reviewed.

1. INTRODUCTION

The history of advanced composite materials (ACM) is rather new. They have been mostly introduced in the last two decades but because of their superior strength-to-weight ratio and stiffness-to-weight ratio, they are making a rapid penetration in high valued application where high performance is required. Especially in the aircraft industry, with increasing performance requirements, the airplanes become heavier and more complex and more expensive to build. Metals are being partially replaced by new weight-, cost- and energy saving materials. They are high performance glass fiber, carbon fiber, boron fiber and aramid fiber combined with epoxy, polyimide, or aluminum matrix materials.

Last year there were three remarkable events which make epoch-making footnotes in the history of advanced composite materials application into aircraft. First flight of Lear Fan 2100, 8 seated business jet whose fuselage is made of all advanced composite materials was successfully performed on January 1, 1981. The first space shuttle "Columbia" which is equipped with carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) cargo bay door and many other ACM parts successfully returned on the earth on April 14, 1981. The Number One Boeing 767, Boeing's first new transport of the eighties, which uses significant amount of ACM parts on commercial scale was rolled out from the plant on August 4, 1981 and it made a successful first flight on September 30, 1981. These events have been proving that ACM is well accepted as a structural materials. Nowadays, it is becoming a general tendency that most of the newly designed aircraft utilize significant quantity of advanced composite materials in the structural components including secondary structures and primary structures.

It is true that most of those remarkable developments of ACM into aircraft application have been mainly carried out in the United States and Europe. Very little activities of such kind of developments have been reported in the Japanese aircraft industry. It can be said that major application of ACM in Japan is rather limited in premium sporting goods such as fishing rods, golf club shafts, tennis rackets etc.. However Japanese industry does play an important role in terms of reinforcement fiber production, especially carbon fiber production. In this paper, then, the status of Japanese reinforcement fiber production, spotlighting mainly on the carbon fiber production and its application developments in the industrial area will be discussed.

2. CARBON FIBER (CF)

2.1 HISTORY OF CARBON FIBER (CF) DEVELOPMENT

Carbon fiber (CF) is not exactly a new material. In fact, in the 1870's researchers on the electric light bulb discovered that a carbonized cotton thread would glow brightly when endorsed in a vacuum and fed a shot of electricity. And in 1880, Thomas A. Edison received a patent on his "incandescent carbon filament lamp".

However there has been a long silence of carbon fiber until early 1950's. In October 1957, first satellite "Sputnik" has been launched by Russia for the first time of human history. Since then the competition of the space exploration between U.S.A. and Russia has broken out. And it has stimulated to a search for the new materials which can meet the aerospace requirements. Carbon fiber has come into the spotlight as the aerospace materials.

Firstly, carbon fiber was manufactured from rayon fiber. They have been combined with phenolic resins and used as an ablative material for rocket nozzle or reentry nose where its refractoriness and high heat resistance have proved valuable.

In 1959, the first commercial carbon fiber with high strength and high modulus properties has been introduced into a market under a tradename of "Thornel 25" by Union Carbide. It was manufactured from rayon and it had a Young's Modulus of 25 msi (million pounds per square inches) and main application was the structural reinforcement for plastic composites. It was an epoch-making event for carbon fiber history.

Carbon fiber itself is insoluble and will not melt, thus it can not be extruded or spun directly. Carbon fiber must be derived from other fibers which contain carbon and which will be carbonized through the use of heat under closely controlled conditions which may involve the use of other chemicals or gases.

In parallel with the introduction of "Thornel 25" based on rayon fiber, an intensive research work has been carried out to find the more suitable raw materials for carbon fiber ("precursor") in UK and in Japan. Dr. Shindo, Osaka Industrial Institute of Japan has succeeded in making carbon fiber from acrylic fiber in 1959 firstly in the world and got basic patent of PAN (polyacrylonitrile) based CF production in Japan. The scientists of RAE (Royal Aircraft Establishment, U.K.) also have invented the manufacturing technology of carbon fiber based on PAN in 1963. The mechanical properties of them were far excellent compared with that of rayon based carbon fiber. Since then, PAN has established the position of precursor (raw material) and still the most important precursor for structural use carbon fiber.

Nowadays more than 90% of structural use CF is based on PAN precursor. The rest of only less than 10% is shared by rayon based and pitch based CF. One of the remarkable characteristics of pitch based CF is that they can offer superior high modulus properties compared to PAN based CF; e.g. high Young's Modulus (350 GPa to 750 GPa) is obtainable at less expensive cost. Main application of these fibers can be found in the area of aerospace application such as satellite, space shuttle and carbon/carbon composites.

2.2 HISTORY OF PAN BASED CF DEVELOPMENT IN JAPAN

In review of carbon fiber development in Japan (Table 1), Nippon Carbon and Tokai Electrode (now Tokai Carbon) were the pioneers in the development of PAN based CF. They have been investigating on commercialization of PAN based CF on the basis of Dr. Shindo's basic patent since 1959.

In 1962, Nippon Carbon started commercial production of PAN based CF at the scale of 0.5 ton per month. They are originally the manufacturer of carbon or graphite products and they are the expert of heat treatment process. But their handicap lay that they were in the position to secure the good PAN precursor from outside the company. Thenafter, the producers of acrylic fiber have joined in the race of PAN based CF development. Toray and Toho Beslon started commercialization of PAN based CF in 1971 and 1973 respectively.

They are the expert in the field of PAN precursor production and are in the position to develop the most suitable precursors which bring out the best quality carbon fiber properties. There has been a remarkable improvement in the properties of carbon fiber. Uniform mechanical properties have been appreciated by the users. The designers and fabricators of the composite are certainly becoming confident of using those carbon fiber materials for structural use application which can meet aerospace requirements.

2.3 PAN BASED CF PRODUCTION IN JAPAN

Table 2 shows the production capacity of worldwide PAN CF producers. There are many extensive expansion programs expected in near future. Japanese producers play an important role in the supply of PAN CF. Especially in terms of supply of high quality PAN precursor for carbon fiber, Japanese producers dominate worldwide market. Toho Beslon, Sumika-Hercules and Mitsubishi Rayon supply PAN precursor to the US CF producers, Celanese, Hercules and HITCO

respectively. On the other hand, Toray have licensed their technology to produce precursor to Union Carbide instead of supplying it from Japan. It is the characteristics of this business where there are close international co-operation between the world producers.

Fig. 1 shows PAN CF demand and supply by country in 1981. We estimate worldwide PAN based CF market volume as follows;

1974	100	ton/year
1977	275	
1978	350	
1979	540	
1980	840	
1981	1,250	

Our estimation shows that out of 1,250 ton, Japanese producers control approximately 60% (750 ton) of worldwide CF production, United State producers produce approximately 30% (375 ton) and European producers, the remainder 10% (125 ton) in 1981.

But the proportions of world capacity are likely to shift in the near future because Union Carbide and Celanese have built their own CF production facilities under Japanese licensed technology in 1982. And aerospace demand in the United States is expected to provide a growing market from now, year by year, for the U.S. producers' increased output.

With regards to demand of CF in 1981, we estimate that U.S. market shares 63% (790 ton) of worldwide CF demand (1,250 ton), Japanese market shares approximately 20% (270 ton) and European market shares 11% (140 ton). The remainder of 4% (50 ton) was shared by others (mainly Taiwan & Korea). The forecast of the worldwide CF market growth for 1980 through 1985 is shown in Table 3.

2.4 CARBON FIBER APPLICATION IN JAPAN

In Japan, sporting goods application have supported the carbon fiber market since carbon fiber introduction into market in early 1970's. Especially golf club shaft and fishing rod were the first big volume applications of carbon fiber in Japan and even in the U.S.A.. Afterwards, there has been a steady shift from sporting goods to aerospace and industrial application in the major share of CF in the U.S.A. and Europe. But in Japan, sporting goods application still maintain a significant market share. This is the characteristics of Japanese CF market. Estimated demand of PAN CF by application in 1981 is shown in Table 4.

Approximately 210 ton of high performance CF (78% of total consumption) went into sporting goods application in Japan in 1981. This high share of sporting goods application in Japan shows a high contrast to Europe where only 21% of total CF were consumed in sporting goods application.

Out of the 210 ton of CF used in sporting goods, 65% (137 ton) were consumed in fishing rod, 25% (53 ton) in golf club shaft, the remainder of 10% (20 ton) went into other sporting goods such as tennis racket, badminton shaft, table tennis racket, archery bow, ski, ski-stock etc.. However, we forecast that there will be a little bit of growth chance of CF product for golf club shaft and tennis racket, while in case of fishing rod, further potential growth can be expected.

Regarding aerospace application, Japanese aircraft industry itself is still relatively small in size. Of course this is a promising potential application area of CF. But another several years will be needed until Japanese aircraft industry consumes sizable amount of CF.

Among the various applications, industrial use is believed to be the most potential application area in Japan. Industrial application of CF are very diversified and are very slow to develop. A significant effort and cost should be poured in the developments of CF for industrial applications. Different approach effort from the aerospace application will be necessary to be successful in the industrial applications. For example, emphasis of characteristics of CF composite might be put on other than high stiffness, strength or light-weight.

Some typical industrial applications in Japan are discussed;

Fig. 2 RADIO TELESCOPE

The mirror surface of radio telescope at Tokyo University astronomical observatory which has a diameter of 45m is reinforced by CF composite. Low thermal expansion of CF composite is fully utilized.

Fig. 3 SUBREFLECTOR FOR PARAVOLA ANTENNA

Low thermal expansion property is utilized.

Fig. 4 TV-ANTENNA

Low noise level and anti-corrosion properties of CFRP compared to steel are the advantages. No adhesion of snow to CFRP antenna is also appreciated in the snow fall area.

Fig. 5 X-RAY CASSETTE

The good transparency of carbon fiber to the X-ray makes possible the wide application of CF into a variety of X-ray components such as cassette, pressure plate, X-ray film changer, grid etc..

Fig. 6 X-RAY TABLE BED

X-ray table bed is also manufactured from CF composite and is stiff, strong and light-weight as well as being transparent to X-rays.

Fig. 7 ROBOT (MANIPULATOR)

High stiffness, strong, light weight and good dimensional-stability of CF composite becomes important in precision instrument such as robot, X-Y drawer, micrometer frame etc..

Fig. 8 BOAT & MARINE (REINFORCEMENT & ELECTROMAGNETIC SHIELDING)

Boat and Yacht are reinforced with CF composite. Also CF mat is layed-up on the bridge of fishing boat which provides electromagnetic shielding and allows the long distance radio communication.

Fig. 9 CIVIL ENGINEERING APPLICATION
(HOLDER OF WATER SUPPLY LINE ON THE BRIDGE)

Water supply pipe line is held onto the bridge by the CF composite holder. 25m long holder is supported by the high stiff CF composite. A number of expandable bridge joints which are made of CF cloth are also used in the Japanese elevated motorway.

Fig. 10 AUTOMOTIVE COMPONENTS (DRIVE SHAFT, LEAF SPRING ETC.)

High stiffness, light weight and good vibration damping properties are fully utilized in the automotive components.

Fig. 11 WHEEL CHAIR

Very light weight wheel chair made of CF composite weighs only 10 Kg compared with 20 Kg of conventional steel product.

The abovementioned examples are typical applications in the industrial area. In addition to them, a number of development items are also under way in the area such as camera, radio, TV set, VTR, and computer components where chopped CF are mainly used in combination with thermoplastic resins. A huge number of components can justify rather the tiny consumption of CF per each component. These kind of steady and patient development works in Japanese industry will surely lead to the glorious breakthrough of CF application in industrial usages.

2.5 PITCH BASED CF IN JAPAN

The first pitch based CF was developed by Prof. Ohtani, University of Gumma, Japan, in 1965 who used polyvinylchloride (PVC) pitch as raw material. Nowadays petroleum pitch is used as raw material for pitch based CF. In Japan, Kureha Chemical has started to develop petroleum pitch based CF since 1967 and has built its commercial plant with the capacity of 10 ton per month in 1970. They now operate 240 ton a year plant in full. In the U.S.A., Union Carbide has concentrated their efforts to develop high modulus type of pitch fiber which is different from Kureha pitch fiber, and successfully could build its commercial plant with 200 ton a year capacity in 1981.

Pitch based CF has generally high modulus at the sacrifice of tensile strength. Because of these characteristics, the following applications are under development;

- a) sealing materials such as packing and gasket which utilizes chemical corrosion resistance
- b) heat insulation materials which utilizes heat resistance properties
- c) abrasion materials which utilizes good friction properties
- d) replacement of asbestos

In August 1981, Kyushu Industrial Research Institute announced that they have developed the manufacturing technology of pitch based CF which provides the high tensile strength (more than 3,000 MPa) equivalent to PAN based CF. They claim that they spin the yarn from "pre-mesophase" pitch, instead Union Carbide spins the yarn from "mesophase" pitch.

Other potential applications under investigation include automotive brake pads, cement reinforcement, electrode for fuel cell and radio frequency (RF)/electromagnetic (EM) interference shielding. Also the replacement of asbestos, annual consumption of which reaches to 4-5 million ton, will be the most encouraging application field. Recently, development works of CF utilizing coal tar pitch as raw material have been announced by Sumitomo Metal, Mitsubishi Chemical, Nippon Steel, Mitsui Cokes, etc. in Japan.

3. ARAMID FIBER (Ar F)

Aramid Fiber (ArF) provides higher specific strength and higher impact strength compared with CF. On the other hand, CF offers high stiffness but impact resistance of composite made from it is relatively low. It will be improved by the addition of ArF which has high strain-to-failure. The "hybrid" construction of ArF/CF will continue to find growth in structural composite applications such as aircraft, boat/marine and industrial machinery equipments.

Also by utilizing its unique characteristics of ArF, applications have been extensively developed in the area of tire cord, rope and cable, industrial belt and hose, bullet-proof jacket and protection glove in Japan.

Nowadays Ar F in Japanese market is almost dominated by Du Pont's product "Kevlar". Current market volume of Ar F in Japan is estimated to be approximately 300 ton per year. In along with the market growth, Teijin (Ar F "HM-50") and Asahi Chemical are said to have commercialization plans of Ar F in the near future. Break down of Ar F applications in Japan is estimated as follows;

composite (incl. boat/marine)	12 %
rope, cable, belt, hose	15 %
tire cord	70 %
others (incl. ballistic)	3 %
<hr/>	
total	100 %

Potential application includes replacement of asbestos in the concrete reinforcement from the view point of alkali-resistant property.

4. SILICONE CARBIDE FIBER (Si C F)

Carbon Fibers have some disadvantages;

CF has poor wet-ability with metal matrix, therefore tensile strength of the composite decreases as CF reacts to oxidize at the presence of oxygen from the temperature of 400°C. Accordingly, it is not suitable for applications such as nuclear reactor where super high temperature resistance is required.

In order to meet such requirements, metal matrix composite (MMC) which can stand at high temperature has been developed. In 1975, Prof. Yajima, Tohoku University has developed Silicone Carbide Fiber (SiCF) and Nippon Carbon has succeeded in producing SiCF at pilot plant scale under his technology licence. The properties of their SiCF are as follows;

Tensile Strength: 2,500 - 3,000 MPa
 Young's Modulus : 2,000 GPa
 Density : 2.55
 Thermal Coefficient of Expansion : $3.1 \times 10^{-6} \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}$
 Maximum Usage Temperature : 1,250 °C

There are no remarkable degradation in tensile strength and Young's Modulus up to 1,200°C. Potential applications of MMC such as Aluminum and Titanium include aircraft structural material and automotive engine. Centrifuge rotor for uranium enrichment, meshbelt for continuous heat treatment, high temperature bag filter for antipollution, catalyst holder for automotive exhaust gas treatment and heat resistant conveyer belt are the development items under investigation.

Nippon Carbon is scheduled to build 1 ton per month SiCF plant in 1982 under Japanese Government support.

Year	Major Events
1880	Mr. Thomas A. Edison applied patent on incandescent carbon filament lamp.
1950's	Carbon fiber based on rayon was used as an ablative material for the use of rocket nozzle or reentry nose.
1959	Union Carbide (USA) introduced rayon based CF under tradename of "Thornel 25". Dr. A. Shindo, Osaka Industrial Institute (Japan), applied basic patent of PAN based CF.
1962	Nippon Carbon (Japan) started to make <u>low modulus</u> PAN based CF (0.5 ton/month).
1963	Dr. Watt & Dr. Johnson, Royal Aircraft Establishment (RAE) (UK) succeeded in manufacturing high quality carbon fiber from PAN.
1964	Courtaulds, Morganite and Rolls Royce (UK) started manufacturing of PAN based CF based on RAE technology.
1965	Prof. Ohtani, Gumma University (Japan) developed pitch based CF.
1969	Courtaulds (UK) and Nippon Carbon (Japan) commercialized <u>high performance</u> PAN based CF.
1970	Kureha Chemical (Japan) commercialized pitch based CF (10 ton/month).
1971	Toray (Japan) commercialized PAN based CF (1 ton/month).
1972	Hercules (USA) started production of PAN based CF.
1973	Toho Beslon (Japan) commercialized PAN based CF (0.5 ton/month).
1974	"Boom" of carbon fiber golf club shaft and fishing rod.

Table 1 BRIEF HISTORY OF CARBON FIBER DEVELOPMENT

	Manufacturer	Tradename	Capacity (1981)	Capacity (end of 1982)	Remarks
Japan	Toray	TORAYCA	420	1,260	
	Toho Beslon	BESFIGHT	240	900	
	Nippon Carbon (Asahi-Nippon Carbon Fiber)	CARBOLON	60	180	
	Mitsubishi Rayon	PYROFIL	-	120	
	Sumika-Hercules	MAGNAMITE	-	-	Importing CF from Hercules
	U.S.A.	Hercules	MAGNAMITE	250	450
Union Carbide		THORNEL	-	360	
Celanese		CELION	-	120	Importing PAN from Toho Beslon
Hitco		HI-TEX	115	115	Importing PAN from Mitsubishi
Stackpole Great Lakes Carbon		PANEX FORTAFIL	25 15	25 15	
Europe	Courtaulds	GRAFIL	360	360	
	Sigri	SIGRAFIL	-	-	
	Serofim	RIGILOR	20	20	

Table 2 ANNUAL PRODUCTION CAPACITY OF PAN BASED CF MANUFACTURERS

(ton/year)

	1980	1981	1982	1983	1984	1985
U.S.A.	500	790	840	1,260	2,000	3,000
EUROPE	100	140	250	350	480	640
JAPAN	220	270	380	500	600	800
OTHERS	20	50	150	200	240	310
TOTAL	840	1,250	1,620	2,310	3,320	4,750

Table 3 FORECAST OF WORLDWIDE CF MARKET GROWTH

(ton/year)

	AEROSPACE	SPORTS	OTHERS	TOTAL
U.S.A.	400	160	230	790
EUROPE	70	30	40	140
JAPAN	10	210	50	270
OTHERS	—	50	—	50
TOTAL	480	450	320	1,250

Table 4 ESTIMATED DEMAND BY APPLICATION (1981)

Fig. 4 TV-ANTENNA

Fig. 5 X-RAY CASSETTE

Fig. 6 X-RAY TABLE BED

Fig. 7 ROBOT (MANIPULATOR)

Fig. 8 BOAT & MARINE
(REINFORCEMENT &
ELECTROMAGNETIC SHIELDING)

Fig. 9 CIVIL ENGINEERING APPLICATION
(HOLDER OF WATER SUPPLY LINE
ON THE BRIDGE)

Fig. 10 AUTOMOTIVE COMPONENTS
(DRIVE SHAFT, LEAF SPRING ETC.)

Fig. 11 WHEEL CHAIR